

DiSSCo Flanders 2.0: Communication Plan

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1. Purpose and structure of the communication plan

Project title	DiSSCo Flanders 2.0: Enhancing access to Flemish collections through integration with DiSSCo
Project ID	FWO project I001625N
Project partners	The DiSSCo Flanders consortium: MeiseBG, INBO, KU Leuven, KMDA, VLIZ, EV-ILVO, UGent, ITM, UHasselt, UAntwerp, VUB, VBTA, RBSZ, dOMG-VPO, RBINS, RMCA, ULB, UNamur, UMons, ULiège, UCLouvain.
Scope	The communication plan discusses <u>external</u> communication of the DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 project.
Purpose	This communication plan is a tool to ensure effective, consistent, and timely communication from the project partners to all stakeholders of DiSSCo Flanders. This communication plan is linked to Work Package 1 (WP1), mainly Task 1.3 <i>Outreach and communication</i> .
Structure	This communication plan consists of a document that explains the main project messages, communication plan objectives, target audience, communication channels, and communication guidelines. The document is linked to a dynamic spreadsheet, containing the “living” communication matrix. The spreadsheet can be more easily updated throughout the project. It centralises all communication ambitions and logs all communication activity.
Implementation	To ensure that this document is used throughout the four year project, we instate a communication team. This team will keep the usage of the communication plan relevant during the project and will evaluate the effectiveness of the communication. It consists of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ILVO: Liselot Breyne - MeiseBG: Jonas Depecker - Ghent University: Steven Verstockt - KMDA: Zjef Pereboom

2. Project message

Main project message: DiSSCo Flanders is a Research Infrastructure (RI) nested in the European Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo), aimed at unlocking natural science collections and specimen data from the DiSSCo Flanders consortium through a digital one-stop shop, which enhances their findability and accessibility and leads to accelerated research. The DiSSCo Flanders project allows maturing both the physical and digital management of the collections of the consortium, while also contributing to the DiSSCo services for global research access, such as maintaining a crowdsourcing platform, and developing standards and AI-tools for data extraction.

Important messages of the project

- The DiSSCo Flanders project enables unlocking the specimens and collections present in the DiSSCo Flanders consortium to become FAIR digital objects. (Work Package 2)
- The DiSSCo Flanders project provides a performant crowdsourcing platform: DoeDat, as a DiSSCo service at the European level. (Work Package 3)
- The DiSSCo Flanders project offers services facilitating taxonomic research on specimens, such as an application allowing linkage of taxonomic data scattered in different online databases and methods to extract information from historic taxonomic literature. (Work Package 4)
- The DiSSCo Flanders project supports researchers and collection managers with practical guidelines and templates allowing mobilisation of physical specimens and working with collections from colonial contexts. (Work Package 5)
- The DiSSCo Flanders project provides enrichment tools as a DiSSCo service at the European level, fine-tuning the segmentation, recognition, and geolocalisation for both 2D and 3D digitised imagery. (Work Package 6)
- The DiSSCo Flanders project supports the communities linked to the research infrastructure by providing training for collection managers and research projects for students. (Work Package 7)

Project title and slogan: DiSSCo Flanders 2.0: Enhancing access to Flemish collections through integration with DiSSCo.

3. Communication objectives

The outcomes of DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 are relevant for a broad and diverse audience, necessitating a carefully tailored communication plan to effectively convey key findings. Strategic communication is essential to maximising the project's impact and supporting long-term knowledge exchange. To this end "Task 1.3 *Outreach and communication*" and this document "Communication Plan: DiSSCo Flanders 2.0" was created. Finalised in month 6 of the project (June 2025), this plan outlines the following key objectives:

- To raise awareness about the DiSSCo Flanders infrastructure, consortium, and project and to illustrate the importance of (digitised) natural science collections.
- To inform stakeholders of project milestones, progress, and outcomes and how to use the Research Infrastructure.
- To encourage engagement from researchers, policy makers, and the public and inspire new collaborations.

4. Target audience

The **target audience** for the DiSSCo Flanders communication can be any of the stakeholders, depending on the message we want to bring across. An overview of the different identified stakeholders is given in [Table 1](#).

Each of these stakeholders can be mapped according to the importance and influence they have on the DiSSCo Flanders project and infrastructure. This is called the **stakeholder mapping**, for we have identified four classes ([Table 2](#)).

Table 2: Stakeholder mapping based on the importance and influence stakeholders have on the DiSSCo Flanders project and infrastructure.

	Little importance	High importance
Little influence	Monitor	Inform
High influence	Report	Participate

Importance means that the project is important to this specific stakeholder. The stakeholder is interested in the results of this project / research infrastructure for his/her own work.

Influence means that the stakeholder has power over the success of the project. The stakeholder can determine the success or failure of the project / research infrastructure.

Each of the stakeholders can be appointed a priority. Considering **priority** we have two classes:

- (1) **Primary:** they need to hear [the project messages](#).
- (2) **Secondary:** if they also hear [the project messages](#), that's good, but not a goal to strive to.

[Table 1](#) provides an overview of the different stakeholders alongside the class and priority that these have been assigned to. It furthermore lists a set of preferred communication channels per stakeholders, which are discussed at length in the next section. For the **DiSSCo Flanders stakeholder meetings** MeiseBG will invite representatives of all groups below (including the project partners). Because this communication channel applies to all stakeholders, it is not added in the communication channel column.

Table 1: An overview of the stakeholders, which could be the target audience of the DiSSCo Flanders communication. For each stakeholder / target audience, the result of the target mapping and their priority levels, along with the proposed communication channels for each group are given.

Stakeholders	Stakeholder mapping	Priority	Communication channel
DiSSCo EU Partners	Participate	Primary	General assembly of DiSSCo EU Social media Conferences (international) DiSSCo EU project meetings DiSSCo EU newsletter DiSSCo CSO (Coordination and

			Support Office)
Project partners	Participate	Primary	DiSSCo Flanders meetings Mailing lists
Academic researchers (including PhD students)	Inform / participate	Primary	Newsletter (DiSSCo EU, institute, ..) Social media Publications / Reports Intranet Workshops Mailing lists
Supporting roles in academics (e.g., Data Stewards, Data managers, Data publishers)	Inform	Primary	Newsletter (DiSSCo EU, institute, ..) Social media Publications / Reports Open Science fora (e.g., basecamp) Conference contribution Hackathon
Industry and private companies	Inform	Secondary	Project brochure Project website Social media Press release
Government and policy makers	Report	Primary	Social media Project brochure Press release Government documents
Funding agencies	Report / Inform	Primary / Secondary	Social media Project brochure Press release Government documents
Citizen scientists	Participate	Primary	Social media Press release DoeDat website Scivil - Flemish knowledge centre for citizen science
Management boards of the participating	Report	Secondary	Newsletter (DiSSCo EU, institute, ..) Publications / reports

institutes			Project brochure Intranet Government documents
General public	Monitor	Secondary	Social media Project website DoeDat website Press release
(University) Students (non PhD)	Monitor (exception: Participate for T7.4 and subcontracting)	Secondary (Primary)	Project website Intranet Mailing lists
Volunteers (other)	Monitor	Secondary	Mailing lists Oral communication
Other Research Infrastructures	Participate	Primary	Social media Newsletter (DiSSCo EU, institute, ..)

Below we elaborate on the different stakeholder groups, which can be the target group of the communication:

- **DiSSCo EU Partners:** Because the DiSSCo Flanders project and infrastructure contribute to the DiSSCo EU RI, it is important that the EU level partners are informed about our project and ambitions to contribute to the DiSSCo services. This ensures alignment with DiSSCo services, helps prevent duplication of effort, and guarantees compatibility between the DiSSCo RI and the collections managed within DiSSCo Flanders. Active engagement (“Participate”) with these stakeholders is crucial, hence, they represent a primary audience for most of our external communication. We aim to keep them informed about our initiatives and outcomes to strengthen collaboration and coherence across the broader DiSSCo network. This is visible in the DiSSCo 2.0 project as there is a separate task of WP1 Task 1.2: *DiSSCo governance and link with other ESFRI’s* focusing on this collaboration.
- **Researchers & academics:** This stakeholder group is a primary target because they are the intended users of both the physical and digital collections. Their feedback and use-cases are essential for optimising the DiSSCo Flanders infrastructure. Our main communication goal is to keep them well informed, so they can easily discover and access the collections and services we provide, and use the DiSSCo Flanders specimens in their research projects. However, secondary, we also need active participation from the researchers. On one hand, we rely on their input to refine and improve the infrastructure; on the other hand, we need them to implement workflows and systems that align with the DiSSCo framework, in their research practices.
- **Supporting roles in academics (e.g., Data stewards, Data managers):** These roles are important catalysts for DiSSCo. The goal is for them to be familiar with the infrastructure and recommend it as a tool for the projects they support.

Supporting roles such as (FOSB) Data stewards often provide training: the goal is that DiSSCo is part of their standard training repertoire. Lastly, these roles are often also consulted and included in making policies and procedures for their institutes, making it important that they include using and publishing to DiSSCo as the norm.

- **Industry and private companies:** While they are not the main users of the DiSSCo Flanders infrastructure, it is important to inform them about the collections, services, and expertise we offer. By showcasing use-cases and research using the RI, we could inspire industry and private companies to reuse the (open source) methods linked to the RI or use the open data of the RI and its linked research, with the overall goal to accelerate the production and services that fulfill societal needs.
- **Government and policymakers:** Their support is essential to the long-term success and sustainability of DiSSCo Flanders and the European DiSSCo RI. It is therefore crucial to keep them well informed and supportive by clearly communicating the scientific and societal value of the infrastructure. Our communication with this group focuses on the relevance of DiSSCo Flanders in areas such as research excellence, biodiversity conservation, digital transformation, and (inter)national collaboration. We aim to show how the project aligns with national and European policy priorities, contributing to open science, sustainable development, and innovation. By sharing progress and outcomes, we build trust and maintain political and financial (see Funding agencies) support.
- **Funding agencies:** In the case of the DiSSCo (Flanders) RI this is currently tightly linked to the stakeholder “Government and policymakers”. The funding agencies that have already supported the infrastructure (WEWIS, FWO) are essential to report to, as they have invested in the project and have to oversee the progress and outcomes. Other funding agencies, not currently directly investing in the DiSSCo (Flanders) RI, should be aware of this infrastructure, facilitating new research projects using or creating specimens, towards the usage of the RI or contributing to the RI, respectively.
- **Citizen scientists:** Their active participation is essential for enriching our data, supporting research, and fostering public engagement with biodiversity. Through platforms like DoeDat, we aim to invite and empower citizens to contribute to science. Our communication focuses on challenging and activating the citizen scientists by fostering community-collaboration and emphasising the importance of many small contributions making a big impact. By keeping citizen scientists informed, motivated, and connected to the outcomes of their work, we foster long-term engagement and strengthen the link between science and society.
- **General public:** While not direct users and hence no primary targets of our communication, we do see value in engaging the broader public to spike interest in biodiversity and the value of natural science collections. It is not a goal to promote the project itself, but rather to highlight the importance of Natural Science collections and how new technologies enhance their accessibility. Through our communication we wish to encourage the general public’s curiosity and appreciation for the collision of the natural world and technologies extracting data from nature. This helps build a positive environment for the project’s long-term impact and societal relevance.
- **Management boards of the participating institutes:** The management of the partner institutes are stakeholders to report to. Since collection management may not be their primary focus (e.g., research institutes such as ILVO, INBO, Universities *versus* collection institutes, musea), it is important to clearly communicate the value and impact of collection management and DiSSCo Flanders. By highlighting how the project supports and enhances research, and raises the institute’s profile, we ensure continued backing and alignment with the institute’s broader goals. Reporting to management helps maintain their commitment

(i.e., the institutes are co-funders given the in-kind contributions) and fosters a supportive environment for the project's success.

- **(University) Students:** Overall, these are not the primary target audience of the DiSSCo Flanders infrastructure; however, they become relevant as they have the potential to be the researchers of tomorrow. Hence, this is a stakeholder group to monitor. It is an added value if students are introduced early to the infrastructure (e.g., during their master thesis), fostering long-term engagement and potential future collaboration. Hence, it is relevant for the DiSSCo Flanders Research Infrastructure to become embedded in the curricula of higher education, rather than target the students directly. This should be covered by targeting the researchers / academia stakeholders. Although this is a group to monitor, students *can* be involved in tasks, where they step into the role of project partners. For example: in Task 7.3, we specifically aim to engage students by encouraging their participation in bachelor and/or master thesis projects in collaboration with the DiSSCo Flanders consortium. Communication will be very specialised via associated professors using the different communication channels of the universities at hand. Similarly, project partners can also employ university students (i.e., student contracts) to help out (e.g., to record specimens in the institute's CMS). This is again very specialised communication, whereby the students become participants of the project by means of subcontracting.
- **Volunteers:** Overall, this group is not the primary target audience of the DiSSCo Flanders infrastructure. However, they could become participants or project partners if they choose to engage with physical collection management or digitisation activities within the partner institutes. By "volunteers", we refer to individuals outside the Citizen Scientist category, often from existing volunteer pools within the institutes. These are typically individuals whose interests and skills are already known, allowing for more tailored, in-house communication. The extent and nature of their involvement will depend on how each institute manages its volunteers and what potential the project partners see in engaging them. This stakeholder group holds little importance and influence. It is expected to consist mainly of students seeking to gain experience or build their careers, and retired individuals with subject-specific interests, such as botany in the context of the botanical garden. While not a key focus, this group should be monitored for potential interest or future engagement in the project.
- **Other Research Infrastructures:** Not only are other existing research infrastructures considered to be important stakeholders, they are also involved in some of the DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 work packages. Liaising with these research infrastructures is part of Task 1.2 (*DiSSCo governance and link with other ESFRIs*) and is coordinated by MeiseBG. As part of Work Package 3 (*Crowdsourcing as a future DiSSCo service*), 4 (*Collections and taxonomic expertise*), 6 (*Collection enrichment as a service*), and 7 (*Sustainability and business plan*) collaborations will be set up with CLARIAH+, Lifewatch, Plazi, ChecklistBank, BHL, and EMBRC. Nonetheless, the general external communication on the project, and the tasks / work packages they are not involved in directly, should also reach these stakeholders.

Project partners are also listed in the stakeholder table for completeness, as they are important stakeholders of the DiSSCo 2.0 project ("to participate"). External communication will not be directed to the project partners. Internal communication is not specified further in this communication plan, but will be largely covered by regular project partner meetings and communication via a mailing list.

5. Communication channels

We divide the communication channels into five categories: (1) websites, (2) social media, forums, and mailing lists, (3) expert publications (e.g., scientific), (4) non-expert publications, and (5) events.

Category 1: websites

The first category includes websites, where you can find online written communication. They allow for people to learn more about the project and the infrastructure, at their own pace. This includes website visitors that are already aware of the project and its aims, as well as visitors that are directed to these websites via weblinks on e.g., social media.

- DiSSCo Flanders project website (<https://dissco-flanders.be/>). The project website also serves as the portal for the digitised collections of the DiSSCo Flanders consortium institutions.
- DoeDat website (<https://www.doedat.be/>)
- Institutional websites: extranet (e.g., <https://www.plantentuinmeise.be/>, <https://www.vlaanderen.be/inbo/home/>, <https://www.ugent.be/en>)
- Institutional websites: intranet (e.g., <https://intranet.inbo.be/>, <https://intranet.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/nl>, <https://sites.google.com/plantentuinmeise.be/intranet/>, ...)

Category 2: social media, forums, and mailing lists

Social media posts and posts on forums are more of a (short message) “nudge” to bring the target audience to relevant websites, publications, communities or events, and inform about the DiSSCo Flanders services. Social media casts a wider net, while specific forums and mailing lists bring the information to a more specialised public.

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/107378092>
- Bluesky: @disscoflanders.bsky.social (<https://bsky.app/profile/disscoflanders.bsky.social>)
- ResearchGate: the researchers can post their DiSSCo Flanders related outputs on Researchgate
- Open Science forums / mailing lists (e.g., FRDN Knowledge Hub in Basecamp)
- Institutional mailing lists (e.g., to reach out to researchers, students)

Category 3: expert publications

As part of its output, the DiSSCo Flanders project will produce written articles and reports, targeted at experts and stakeholders in the field. These publications will focus on biodiversity informatics, scientific research, and research infrastructures.

- Scientific Publications (Scientific journals, peer-reviewed)
- Reports (Institutional reports, Zenodo publications)
- Government documents (e.g., Flemish guide of infrastructures)

Category 4: non-expert publications

Similarly, there will also be articles targeting a broader public:

- Non-scientific DiSSCo Flanders publication (e.g., brochure, leaflet)
- Newsletters (e.g., institutional newsletters, VWI Open Science newsletter, DiSSCo EU newsletter, ...)
- Press release (e.g., to activate citizen scientists into participating on DoeDat)

Category 5: events

Lastly, there will be events organised that require active participation either as an organiser or as a participant. Depending on the message and the target audience, different formats are possible. Usually this involves oral communication / dialogue.

- DiSSCo Flanders user meeting
- Conference contribution
- Workshop
- Hackathon
- General assembly of DiSSCo EU
- DiSSCo EU projects

6. Detailed communication matrix

A communication matrix was developed to inventorise all external communication relating to DiSSCo Flanders. This matrix will furthermore also help with communication planning as different messages can be scheduled and spread in time.

The communication matrix contains the following columns:

- **Comm-ID** = Communication ID. This consists of the task-number (e.g., Task 2.1, followed by an increment consisting of two numbers, e.g., 2.1.01. In this way project partners can easily address a communication event in the list. If the task relates to the project as a whole, it falls under Task 1.3 *Outreach and communication*, with numbers for example 1.3.01, 1.3.02, ...
- **Status**: The status of the communication: planned, executed or canceled.
- **Communication target**: A dropdown from the stakeholders listed in [4. Target Audience](#). Multiple communication targets for one communication action can be selected. More specifications on the target audience (e.g., researchers of KULeuven) can be added in the description.
- **Communication objective**: A dropdown from the objectives listed in [3. Communication objectives](#).
- **Description**: A description of the (planned) communication.
- **Main message**: The main message to communicate.
- **Communication channel**: A dropdown from the communication channels listed in [5. Communication Channels](#).
- **Timing**: The exact timing when the communication will be sent out. Once the exact date is known, the format is: YYYY-MM-DD for example: 2025-05-28. If the exact day is unknown, the format 2025-05-00 should be used. If the exact month and day are unknown, but the year is known the format: 2025-00-00 should be used. If this is a task that needs to be maintained throughout the project (e.g., the project website) it can be coded: 0000-00-00.

This way, the most recent communication will appear at the top of the document when it is sorted by date.

- **Responsible:** The person or institution responsible for the communication. This is an entity, for example INBO or Emily Veltjen.
- **Link:** Once communicated, a weblink to the communication can be given here. This can be a DOI, a link to a social media post, a link to a Google document in the project drive....
- **Evaluation_Type:** Depending on the type of communication (website, social media, written communication, event) this automatically changes to: clicks, likes_reposts, views_downloads or attendees, respectively.
- **Evaluation_score:** This is an optional field. This is a score for the impact of the communication, to help evaluate during the project whether the communication actions are effective. This can be the number of attendees, the number of likes, the number of reposts, the number of views, the number of downloads, and the number of clicks. Example 1: for the LinkedIn post of the DiSSCo Flanders 2 kick-off meeting, we had 74 likes and 8 reposts. Hence the score for likes_reposts (the type) is 74_8. Example 2: The publication: [DiSSCo-Flanders WP2 - task 2.1, Detailed inventory of the collections: Report](#) has 459 views and 383 downloads. Hence, the views_downloads score would be 459_383. These metrics can be recorded for those interested in monitoring the effectiveness of the communication efforts. The communicator and/or communication team can update these numbers where relevant. Sharing this data transparently with fellow project partners, whether the results are successful or not, can support better decision-making for future DiSSCo Flanders 2.0 communications. Some metrics will stabilise quickly. For example, the number of attendees at an event is fixed, and social media engagement (such as likes and reposts) typically plateaus within 2-3 weeks. Others, like website clicks or publication downloads, will continue to increase over time and experience spikes depending on ongoing relevance and visibility. It's important to remember that these figures are only indicative. Many other factors influence the success of a communication activity. For example, timing, the quality of the message, and the choice of visuals. Therefore, metrics should be interpreted within the broader context of each communication action.
- **Recruitment:** This is an optional field. If the message was to recruit participants, it is possible to log the success by monitoring how many participants there were prior to the message and two weeks after the message.

The communication matrix is a “living document”. Project partners can access it via the link below:

[DiSSCo Flanders 2 communicationmatrix](#)

7. Communication guidelines for project partners

To ensure clear, consistent, and professional communication across all channels, the following guidelines have been established. All partners are kindly asked to follow these practices in their project-related communication activities:

- 1) All project partners are requested to consistently mention DiSSCo Flanders in their communications and include a link to the project website ([DiSSCo Flanders](#)).
- 2) Ensure that the term “DiSSCo Flanders” is spelled and capitalised correctly and consistently in all communications.

- 3) In all reports and publications related to the project or that have made use of the DiSSCo Flanders Research Infrastructure, partners must also include the project's name and funding number (I001721N for the first DiSSCo Flanders project (2021-2024), and I001625N for DiSSCo Flanders 2).
- 4) Where applicable, the DiSSCo Flanders logo, the FWO logo, and the WEWIS (Departement Werk, Economie, Wetenschap, Innovatie en Sociale Economie) logo, should be added when project-related content is presented. This could be, but is not limited to, reports, brochures, slides, All logos are collected in [this project folder](#).
- 5) Templates (presentation, report, ...) for DiSSCo Flanders related communication can be found in [this project folder](#).
- 6) All communication activities must be documented in the communication matrix (available [here](#)).
- 7) To support the visibility of the project, partners are encouraged to contribute content to the DiSSCo Flanders website. Contributions to the website can be placed in [this project folder](#). Every 6 months there will be a call for contributions by the website manager.
- 8) For social media outreach, partners who wish to add a post to DiSSCo Flanders' official accounts can upload their materials (text and images) to the designated [project folder](#) and notify the communication team accordingly.
- 9) When posting on social media, the official DiSSCo Europe and DiSSCo Flanders accounts should be tagged and the use of hashtags (e.g., #DiSSCo #DiSSCoFlanders) is encouraged to increase visibility. Additional hashtags that might be relevant are: #AskACurator, #burgerwetenschap, #citizenscience, #DigitalSpecimens, #DigitalExtendedSpecimen, #FairData, #FossilFriday, #MineralMonday, #MolluscMonday, #museumcollection, #NaturalHistory, #NaturalScience, #naturalsciencecollections, #SpecimenOfTheWeek, #TaxonomicTuesday, #taxidermy, ...
- 10) Ensure that all images or videos used in communication materials have the proper permissions (especially when including identifiable individuals) and credits (respecting intellectual property).
- 11) Where possible, and in cases where this is considered an added value, key materials or summaries can be translated into Dutch, French and/or English to maximise outreach across Belgium and Europe.
- 12) Publications (e.g., articles, reports) are made Open Access publishing them in Open Access journals, platforms (e.g., Zenodo) or institutional websites, or [by greenrouting the publication after 6 months](#). A Creative Common (CC) license is used.

8. Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the [INBO team Communication](#) for their (internal) guidance document on: "How to make a communication plan" that we have used for this DiSSCo Flanders communication plan. We also want to highlight the importance of the INBO Open Science cafés, as both the inspirational talk and workshop on communication plans back in 2022, have now proven to be relevant to writing a communication plan in 2025, and have even briefly crossed institutional boundaries with this collaborative project.

We also acknowledge FWO for this opportunity to work further on the DiSSCo Flanders RI for the upcoming four years, as well as the management of all participating institutions supporting their staff involved in collection management to be part of this consortium and project.